

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF INDUCTIVE AND DEDUCTIVE APPROACHES IN TEACHING PRESENT SIMPLE VERB FORMS

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***Abstract:** The article explores the advantages and disadvantages of inductive and deductive approaches in teaching Present Simple verb forms, analyzes the lessons using both methods, which allows to draw conclusions about the feasibility of using the inductive method in teaching English grammar.*

***Key words:** inductive approach, deductive approach, Present Simple verb forms, explicit approach, implicit approach, innovative teaching method.*

Learning grammar is an exciting process that introduces new concepts to the world, allows one to understand better the culture and traditions of a native speaker. Well-formed grammar skills can make speech correct and facilitate the communication process. Currently, grammar occupies a worthy place in teaching foreign languages as Richard and Renandya (2010) explain, “without studying grammar, students' speech skills would be very limited”. There are two main approaches in teaching grammar:

1. Explicit (based on strictly following grammar rules)
2. Implicit (with no focus on grammar rules).

Within the framework of each of these approaches, two main methods have been formed, which are rooted in the strategy of these approaches, but differ significantly in principles, practical techniques, and sequence of actions.

At the present stage, these methods are rarely utilized in their "pure form". In the practice of teaching a foreign language, the teacher may vary the use of certain methods. The choice of the method depends on the age, the level of language

competence of students, the objectives of the course, as well as the features of the grammatical material itself.

The most widespread currently in the practice of teaching grammar is a differentiated approach based on the selective use of the provisions of two traditionally established approaches.

Within the framework of the implicit approach (without explaining the rules), a structural method is used, which is based on exercises for processing structural models, as well as a communicative method, which is characterized by the formation of grammatical skills in speech, i.e. familiarization and training are included in language practice. Grammatical phenomena are studied and assimilated not as a "form" and "structure", but as a means of expressing certain thoughts and communicative intentions. Learning takes place on a situational-functional basis, i.e. from the situation to the grammatical means used in speech. This method helps to implement the principle of communication and diversify speech contexts, but the creation of a truly speech environment presents certain inclinations.

The explicit approach (with an explanation of the rules) includes two methods – deductive and inductive. The deductive approach includes traditional teaching methods while the inductive approach reflects modern methodology and practice.

The deductive approach represents traditional teaching style, because first students learn grammatical structures and rules. This approach has a certain similarity with the grammar-translation method. The main task of students is to acquire grammatical structures and the rules. After, the teacher explains the syntactic constructions in each case.

The inductive approach is modern style of teaching, when new grammatical constructions and rules are presented to students in a real language context.

As in the case of the direct method, students are taught the structure of the language in a "real" situation, that is, in context. The structure of the sentence and text is understood during practice, that is, examples from real life are taken – subjects in the classroom, restaurant menus, posters, travel brochures, etc. are considered.

Both of these methods have their advantages and disadvantages. The deductive approach can be effective for those students who have already mastered the basic grammar structures of the language.

The inductive approach will allow students to operate with the language themselves, thereby confirming learning by practice. The inductive method is considered very effective in teaching English as a second language. However, it seems difficult for students accustomed to traditional teaching methods. Therefore, the teacher should be aware of the preparation and level of students, as well as take into account the objectives of the course and the features of the grammatical material in order to organize the lesson in a more productive way. Let us consider the use of deductive and inductive methods in teaching the tenses of the verb of the Simple group and analyze the advantages and disadvantages of both methods.

With the deductive approach, a rule is first studied, usually formulated using specific grammatical terms. For example, Present Simple denotes an ordinary, repetitive action, well-known truths, or an action that occurs on a regularly basis. Then students find this grammatical phenomenon or structure in sentences or in the text, name its form, explain in what meaning it is used in this context. These can be individual sentences, examples from fiction or short stories, short dialogues. Below are the sentences with verbs in the form of Present Simple:

- *He works at the college.*
- *Water boils at 100 °C.*
- *The train arrives at 2 o'clock.*
- *He goes to the gym every day*

Then the substitution exercises are performed by analogy with the sample. Then there is a transition to transformation exercises in accordance with the rule. Translation exercises are completed from the native language into English language. Students also compose situational texts, dialogues, interviews using the studied time, which provides an opportunity to use the studied structures in discourse. Thus, the lesson conducted based on the deductive method consists of three stages: presentation, practice and production (PPP).

Undoubtedly, this method has its advantages, as it implements the principles of consciousness, science, contributes to the formation of educational skills and abilities, can be used in independent work. It should also be noted some disadvantages: the difficulty of understanding grammatical terminology, grammar is often practiced on "faceless" sentences, outside of a coherent speech context. As a result, students correctly formulate the rule, explain the use of this time by examples, but find it difficult to use the acquired skill in speech.

Let us also consider the inductive method of teaching (from the individual to the general), in which students formulate a rule themselves, trying to comprehend a grammatical phenomenon through the context, determine its form and find out the patterns of its use. This approach has received the term Guided Discovery. Proponents of this method (Harmer, Scrivener) believe that students perceive the material provided to them better if they analyze the phenomena and formulate the rule themselves.

The lesson consists of the following stages. First, a text or a set of sentences is given, where a new grammatical phenomenon often occurs, including in contrast with already known grammatical phenomena / forms / structures. For example: Present Simple – Past Simple.

He goes to the gym every day. – He went to the gym yesterday.

It is appropriate to use various hints in the text, for example, underlining or highlighting in different colors the features of the form of this grammatical structure, selecting such sentences where the context of using this structure is so unambiguous, clear and transparent that students will be able to easily deduce the rule.

For example:

Yesterday she got up at 7 o'clock and had a big breakfast. She walked to work, which took about half an hour. She started work at 8 o'clock. When she came home she cooked a meal.

The teacher can use concept-checking questions – CCQ to analyze the concept of the context:

Did she get up at 7 yesterday? – Yes, she did.

Did she walk to work today? – No, she didn't.

Does the text refer to the present or past? – To the past.

Next, students formulate the rules of the grammatical structure, corrected by the teacher. The teacher can use an already formed rule with missing terms:

Present Simple or Past Simple.

... is used to express an action which took place in the Past.

... is used to express habitual, repeated action.

After passing through the three-time forms of the Present Simple Tense, exercises are conducted to consolidate all three times.

At the final stage, various types of work are carried out to consolidate the material covered and use it in speech: drawing up dialogues, description of the picture, presentations, discussions on the proposed topics. Tests are conducted to check the material presented, correct the spotted errors. Then you can repeat the test (TTT – test, teach, test).

The inductive method has certain advantages, as it provides the implementation of problem-based learning and stimulates independent language observation. This method develops a guess based on the context and contributes to better memorization of the material being studied. However, it should be noted that not all linguistic phenomena can be explained inductively and learning by this method can take a lot of time. The choice of one or another method is determined by several factors: learning objectives, the level of students, the nature of grammatical material. While explaining the tense forms of the verb, in particular the Simple Tense, it is advisable to use the inductive method, since this material allows for the derivation of the rule by context by the students themselves. The use of the inductive method is possible in the classroom, where students already have some basic knowledge of English, which will allow using the "Guided Discovery" method of learning. The lesson conducted using this method will be interesting and rich, contributing to the development of language guesswork and observation among students.

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